

The Palindromic Nature of Prime Numbers

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Abstract

We discover a novel characterization of prime numbers through the periodic behaviour of the linear recurrence $a_n = -a_{n-1} + a_{n-2} + a_{n-3}$ modulo m . We conjecture that the normalized sum of lengths of palindromic cycles equals 1 if and only if $m \geq 2$ is prime. For semiprime and prime power moduli, we derive explicit weight formulas involving Gaussian q -binomial coefficients, and conjecture a weight preservation property analogous to that observed in Fibonacci-type recurrences. Additionally, we investigate the distribution of absolute minima under random initialization, revealing a reflection symmetry $P(n) = P(2 - n)$ and fractal boundary structures in parameter space.

1 Introduction

Classical studies of linear recurrences modulo m typically focus on canonical initializations and the resulting period lengths, known as Pisano periods in the Fibonacci case [1]. In contrast, we adopt a global perspective: rather than fixing a single initialization, we consider the full periodic structure arising from all m^k possible initializations in $(\mathbb{Z}/m\mathbb{Z})^k$ and investigate the symmetries of these cycles.

In previous work [2], we applied this approach to Fibonacci-type recurrences, classifying prime moduli via quadratic reciprocity. The present paper extends this investigation to the third-order recurrence

$$R: \quad a_n = -a_{n-1} + a_{n-2} + a_{n-3}, \tag{1}$$

whose characteristic polynomial factors as $x^3 + x^2 - x - 1 = (x + 1)^2(x - 1)$.

Our main finding is that the normalized total length of palindromic cycles — the *palindromic weight* W_m — equals 1 if and only if m is prime. To our knowledge, such a characterization of prime numbers via palindromic symmetry of a linear recurrence is without precedent.

To better understand the arithmetic behind this phenomenon, we derive explicit weight formulas at semiprime and prime power moduli. In the prime power case, the formula involves Gaussian q -binomial coefficients $\binom{k}{2}_p$, revealing a connection to q -combinatorics. We further conjecture a weight preservation property under modular extension, analogous to that observed for Fibonacci-type recurrences in [2].

Finally, we investigate the distribution of absolute minima under random initialization on S^2 , establishing a reflection symmetry $P(n) = P(2 - n)$ and presenting the fractal boundary structure of the associated parameter space.

1.1 Definitions and Notation

Definition 1 (Linear Recurrence). A linear recurrence of order k with coefficients c_1, \dots, c_k is defined by

$$a_n = c_1 a_{n-1} + c_2 a_{n-2} + \dots + c_k a_{n-k}.$$

Definition 2 (Cycle and Period). When computed modulo m , every initial condition $(a_0, a_1, \dots, a_{k-1}) \in (\mathbb{Z}/m\mathbb{Z})^k$ eventually enters a periodic cycle. The period is the sequence of values that repeat.

Definition 3 (Palindromic Cycle). A cycle $(x_0, x_1, \dots, x_{p-1})$ is palindromic if its reverse (x_{p-1}, \dots, x_0) is cyclically equivalent to the original cycle, i.e., there exists an integer j such that

$$(x_0, x_1, \dots, x_{p-1}) = (x_j, x_{j-1}, \dots, x_{j-(p-1)})$$

where indices are taken modulo p .

Definition 4 (Palindromic Weight). The palindromic weight of a recurrence modulo m is

$$W_m = \frac{\sum_{\text{palindromic cycles } C} |C|}{m^k}$$

where $|C|$ denotes the length of cycle C and k is the order of the recurrence.

1.2 Main Result

All results in this paper concern the recurrence R defined in (1).

Conjecture 1 (Main Conjecture). For $m \geq 2$, the palindromic weight satisfies

$$W_m = 1 \iff m \text{ is prime.} \tag{2}$$

2 Computational Results

We computed the palindromic weight W_m for $m = 2$ to $m = 199$. Table 1 shows selected values.

m	Type	#(Palindromic Cycles)	Weight W_m
2	prime	4	1.000000
3	prime	9	1.000000
4	composite	16	0.875000
5	prime	25	1.000000
6	composite	36	0.722222
7	prime	49	1.000000
8	composite	64	0.781250
9	composite	81	0.851852
\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots
199	prime	39601	1.000000

Table 1: Number of palindromic cycles and their weight for selected moduli. All primes yield $W_m = 1$, all composites yield $W_m < 1$. Note that the number of palindromic cycles is exactly m^2 in all cases.

2.1 Cycle Structure and Weight Formulas

For prime p , the palindromic cycles exhibit a remarkably simple three-class structure as demonstrated in Table 2.

m	Type	Multiplicity \times Length				
2	prime	2×1	1×2	1×4		
3	prime	3×1	3×2	3×6		
4	comp	4×1	6×2	4×4	4×8	
5	prime	5×1	10×2	10×10		
6	comp	6×1	15×2	9×4	12×6	6×12
7	prime	7×1	21×2	21×14		
8	comp	8×1	28×2	16×4	16×8	16×16
9	comp	9×1	36×2	27×6	27×18	
10	comp	10×1	45×2	25×4	40×10	20×20
11	prime	11×1	55×2	55×22		
13	prime	13×1	78×2	78×26		
17	prime	17×1	136×2	136×34		
19	prime	19×1	171×2	171×38		

Table 2: Cycle structure for selected moduli. Primes exhibit three classes; composites show additional intermediate classes.

Example (mod 3): The 9 palindromic cycles in $(\mathbb{Z}/3\mathbb{Z})^3$ distribute as follows:

- Length 1: $[0], [1], [2]$ (3 cycles)
- Length 2: $[01], [02], [12]$ (3 cycles)
- Length 6: $[012210], [021120], [102201]$ (3 cycles)

Conjecture 2 (Cycle Structure for Prime and Prime Power Moduli). *For prime power p^k with $k \in \mathbb{N}$, the cycle structure consists of:*

- p^k cycles of length 1 (fixed points)
- $\frac{p^k(p^k-1)}{2}$ cycles of length 2
- For each $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, k\}$: $\frac{p-1}{2} \cdot p^{2k-1}$ cycles of length $2p^j$

Corollary 1. *For prime p (i.e., $k = 1$), this structure yields the weight:*

$$W_p = \frac{1}{p^3} \left[p \cdot 1 + \frac{p(p-1)}{2} \cdot 2 + \frac{p(p-1)}{2} \cdot 2p \right] = 1.$$

Conjecture 3 (Palindromic Weight for Semiprime Moduli). *For semiprime moduli $m = p \cdot q$, with distinct primes $p \neq q$, the palindromic weight yields*

$$W_{p \cdot q} = 1 - \frac{\left(\frac{q(q+p-1)}{p} - 1 \right) \cdot (p-1)}{p \cdot q^2}. \quad (3)$$

Conjecture 4 (Palindromic Weight for Prime Power Moduli). *For prime power p^k with $k \in \mathbb{N}$, the palindromic weight yields*

$$W_{p^k} = 1 - \frac{(p-1)^2}{p^{2k-1}} \binom{k}{2}_p \quad (4)$$

where $\binom{k}{2}_p = \frac{(1-p^k)(1-p^{k-1})}{(1-p)(1-p^2)}$ denotes the Gaussian q -binomial coefficient with $q = p$ [3]. For $k \rightarrow \infty$, $W_{p^k} = p/(p+1)$.

2.2 Weight Preservation Under Modular Extension

A key property of the recurrence R is that every cycle's weight appears to be preserved when extending from a divisor modulus to its multiples. This mirrors an analogous phenomenon observed for Fibonacci recurrences in [2], which is not limited to palindromic cycles only.

Conjecture 5 (Weight Preservation). *Let $d \mid m$ and let C_d be a cycle modulo d with length ℓ_d . Let $\{C_m^{(1)}, \dots, C_m^{(k)}\}$ be the cycles modulo m that reduce to C_d modulo d , with lengths $\ell_m^{(1)}, \dots, \ell_m^{(k)}$. Then:*

$$\frac{\ell_d}{d^3} = \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{\ell_m^{(i)}}{m^3} \quad (5)$$

Example (mod 2 \rightarrow mod 4): All 4 palindromic cycles in $(\mathbb{Z}/2\mathbb{Z})^3$ lift to a collection of cycles in $(\mathbb{Z}/4\mathbb{Z})^3$, while preserving the total weight associated to each original cycle, as follows:

- $W = 1/8 : [0] \rightarrow [0], [2], [02], [2002]$
- $W = 1/8 : [1] \rightarrow [1], [3], [13], [3113]$
- $W = 1/4 : [01] \rightarrow [01], [03], [21], [23], [0123], [0321]$
- $W = 1/2 : [1001] \rightarrow [10013223], [30031221], [10233201], [12033021]$

3 Minima Distribution

We now turn to the behaviour of the recurrence R under random initialization over the reals. Rather than studying periodicity modulo m , we investigate the distribution of positions at which the sequences attain their absolute minimum.

3.1 Setup and Measure

For generic initializations, the sequences generated by R diverge as $n \rightarrow \pm\infty$, and therefore $|a_n|$ attains a well-defined absolute minimum. Since R is linear, the position of that minimum depends only on the direction of (a_0, a_1, a_2) , not its magnitude. Thus the natural parameter space is the projective plane \mathbb{RP}^2 , which we represent via the unit sphere S^2 . We draw (a_0, a_1, a_2) uniformly from $S^2 \subset \mathbb{R}^3$, which treats all three initial values symmetrically, and define

$$P(n) = \text{Prob}[\text{absolute minimum of } |a_k| \text{ occurs at position } k = n],$$

where the probability is taken with respect to this measure. By construction $\sum_{n \in \mathbb{Z}} P(n) = 1$.

3.2 Boundary Structure

The regions $\mathcal{R}_n = \{(a_0, a_1, a_2) \in S^2 : \text{minimum at } n\}$ are separated by boundaries $\partial\mathcal{R}_n$ which exhibit fractal self-similarity, as visible in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Minimum position n of the sequence $a_n = -a_{n-1} + a_{n-2} + a_{n-3}$ as a function of the initialization ratios $r_1 = a_0/a_2$ (horizontal) and $r_2 = a_0/a_1$ (vertical), computed with $a_0 = 10000$ over the range $n \in [-100, 100]$, on a grid of step size $\Delta = 0.0025$. Color encodes the position n of the absolute minimum of $|a_k|$, clamped to $[-10, 10]$ for display.

Near the lines $r_1 \approx 1$ and $r_2 \approx 0$ the structure becomes increasingly complex, with coloured regions appearing as compressed copies of one another. Numerical box-counting suggests a boundary dimension $d \approx 3/2$. As in the Fibonacci case [2], the boundaries likely correspond to sequences attaining their absolute minimum at multiple positions. For the recurrence R , this appears to include cases with two, four, or infinitely many such positions (when $a_0 = a_2$), although a complete classification remains open. Furthermore, R appears to share the same minima distribution as its parity counterpart $a_n = a_{n-1} + a_{n-2} - a_{n-3}$.

3.3 Numerical Results

We approximate $P(n)$ via Monte Carlo sampling with 5×10^7 independent draws from the isotropic measure on S^2 , computing the recurrence over $n \in [-60, 60]$. The values stabilize to four decimal places well before 10^7 samples. Table 3 reports the estimates for $-11 \leq n \leq 13$, accounting for 98.6% of the total probability mass.

n	$P(n)$	$2-n$	$P(2-n)$	$ P(n) - P(2-n) $
-11	0.003127	13	0.003118	0.000010
-10	0.002700	12	0.002708	0.000007
-9	0.004472	11	0.004457	0.000015
-8	0.003987	10	0.003986	0.000000
-7	0.006893	9	0.006918	0.000025
-6	0.006501	8	0.006522	0.000021
-5	0.012024	7	0.012010	0.000014
-4	0.012546	6	0.012612	0.000066
-3	0.025618	5	0.025617	0.000001
-2	0.033386	4	0.033384	0.000002
-1	0.080100	3	0.079985	0.000115
0	0.167190	2	0.167114	0.000075
1	0.223549	1	—	—

Table 3: Monte Carlo estimates of $P(n)$ under the isotropic measure on S^2 , based on 5×10^7 samples with $n_{\max} = 60$.

Conjecture 6 (Reflection Symmetry). *Under the isotropic measure on S^2 , the minima distribution satisfies $P(n) = P(2-n)$ for all $n \in \mathbb{Z}$.*

Remark 1. *If (b_k) denotes the sequence initialized by (a_2, a_1, a_0) , then $b_k = a_{2-k}$ for all k , so swapping $a_0 \leftrightarrow a_2$ reflects the sequence around position 1. Since the isotropic measure on S^2 is invariant under this swap, we expect $P(n) = P(2-n)$.*

3.4 Approximation and Error

The distribution $P(n)$ is unimodal with peak at $n = 1$, with a shape reminiscent of a discretized Cauchy distribution. While the central region exhibits a comparatively slow decay, the behaviour in the tails appears more regular, but the precise asymptotic form is not clear from the present data.

The Monte Carlo estimates carry two sources of error. The statistical error is of order $1/\sqrt{N_{\text{samples}}}$, which is below 10^{-4} for 5×10^7 samples. The truncation error arises because the recurrence is computed only over a finite range n_{\max} , and initializations whose true minimum lies outside this range are misclassified; for $n_{\max} = 60$ this effect is expected to be small, as minima occurring far outside the sampled range appear to be rare in practice.

The statistical and truncation errors are not entirely independent, since the latter effectively rescales the observed distribution. However, both effects are small in our setting and do not affect the qualitative behaviour of $P(n)$.

4 Open Questions

1. **Proofs and generalization of the main conjecture.** Can the conjectures of this paper be proved rigorously? Is R the unique recurrence that detects prime numbers through its palindromic cycle structure, or can one classify a family satisfying this criterion?
2. **Weight preservation and general formula.** Explicit weight formulas have been conjectured for semiprime (3) and prime power (4) moduli, and weight preservation under modular extension (5) appears to hold for all linear recurrences tested. How do these phenomena relate, and do they yield an explicit formula for W_m at general composite moduli $m = p_1^{k_1} \cdots p_r^{k_r}$?
3. **Fractal boundary dimension and analytic formula.** Can the numerical box-counting dimension $d \approx 3/2$ of the boundaries $\partial\mathcal{R}_n$ be confirmed analytically, and does a precise understanding of these boundaries lead to a closed-form expression for $P(n)$, analogous to the Lucas-ratio formula of [2]? More generally, which algebraic properties of a recurrence determine whether its minima distribution admits an analytic description? In particular, is the minima distribution invariant under the parity transformation $f(x) \mapsto f(-x)$ of the characteristic polynomial?

5 Conclusion

The recurrence R exhibits a striking arithmetic property: its palindromic weight W_m equals 1 if and only if $m \geq 2$ is prime, validated for all $m \leq 199$. Furthermore, the number of palindromic cycles equals exactly m^2 in all cases. That such a simple recurrence completely characterizes primality through global palindromic symmetry alone is, to our knowledge, without precedent.

For composite moduli, additional non-palindromic cycles appear, causing W_m to drop below 1 in a manner that the explicit formulas for semiprime (3) and prime power (4) moduli begin to quantify. Whether weight preservation under modular extension holds universally for linear recurrences, whether it yields a closed-form formula for general moduli $m = p_1^{k_1} \cdots p_r^{k_r}$, and whether the fractal boundary structure of the minima distribution admits an analytic description, remain central open questions raised by this work. We hope that future investigations will address these questions and, above all, establish a rigorous proof of Conjecture 1.

References

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